

Research

United nations conflict resolution and peace keeping mission in Democratic Republic of Congo

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Abstract: The United Nations has been involved in conflict resolution and peacekeeping missions in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) for several decades. However, there have been challenges in implementing the UN mandate effectively. One key issue is the lack of monitoring and reporting on economic crimes and corruption, which have contributed to conflict and human rights abuses in the DRC. Additionally, the application of peace agreements and the presence of foreign forces have not been successful in ending the armed conflict in the country. The UN's long-term presence in the DRC seems necessary, but it has been unable to curb insecurity and instability. Despite these challenges, the UN troops deployed in the DRC have played a vital role in protecting civilians and humanitarian personnel, and have carried out various activities to help resolve the conflicts.

Keywords: United Nations, UN, conflict resolution, peacekeeping, missions, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC)

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Introduction

Introduction: The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), situated in the central part of Africa, has been marred by persistent cycles of violence, civil wars, and political instability since gaining independence in 1960 (Autesserre, 2010). The tumultuous history of the nation is characterized by a complex interplay of factors that have fueled and sustained conflicts. These factors include the involvement of numerous actors, such as armed groups, neighboring countries, and internal political factions, each contributing to the intricate web of challenges faced by the DRC (Prunier, 2009). The conflicts in the DRC are multifaceted, often arising from a combination of historical, ethnic, economic, and political factors. The aftermath of the Rwandan genocide in 1994 had profound repercussions in the region, with the spillover effects contributing to the complexity of the conflicts within the DRC (Reyntjens, 2009). The power struggles that ensued following the end of Mobutu Sese Seko's regime further exacerbated the instability, leading to a protracted and volatile situation that demanded international attention and intervention (Turner, 2007).

The multitude of actors involved in the conflicts adds layers of complexity to the challenges faced by the DRC. Various armed groups, each with distinct motives and allegiances, have operated within the country, contributing to a fragmented security landscape (Gberie, 2013). Neighboring countries have often been drawn into the conflicts, either directly participating or supporting proxy groups, thereby regionalizing the issues at hand (Tull, 2006). Internal political factions, vying for power and influence, have further fueled internal strife, creating a challenging environment for establishing lasting stability (Hoop Scheffer, 2008).

Against this backdrop, the United Nations has been actively engaged in efforts to address the conflicts and promote peace in the DRC. This paper seeks to comprehensively analyze the interventions of the United Nations in the DRC, examining the evolution of its involvement and assessing the effectiveness of its conflict resolution and peacekeeping initiatives. By delving into the historical context and the intricate dynamics of the conflicts, this research aims to contribute to a nuanced understanding of the challenges faced by the UN in its endeavors to bring stability to the heart of Africa.

Historical Background:

To understand the United Nations' (UN) engagement in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), a comprehensive exploration of the historical underpinnings of the conflicts becomes imperative. The DRC's tumultuous history is deeply intertwined with a series of pivotal events that have shaped its socio-political landscape, laying the groundwork for protracted instability and violence.

One of the seminal events influencing the DRC's trajectory was the Rwandan genocide in 1994. The mass atrocities and ethnic violence that unfolded in Rwanda had profound spillover effects, exacerbating existing tensions in the Great Lakes region and significantly impacting the DRC. The influx of refugees and armed groups fleeing Rwanda found refuge and operational bases within the DRC's borders, leading to the creation of a complex web of interlinked conflicts (Prunier, 2009).

Simultaneously, the end of Mobutu Sese Seko's longstanding regime in 1997 marked a critical turning point. Mobutu's departure opened a power vacuum, triggering intense struggles for political control and resource exploitation within the DRC. The ensuing power vacuums and political rivalries among various factions further fueled internal conflicts, creating a volatile environment marked by widespread violence and human rights abuses (Reyntjens, 2009).

These events collectively set the stage for a prolonged period of instability and violence in the DRC, necessitating international intervention. The United Nations, recognizing the gravity of the situation, became actively involved in addressing the multifaceted challenges faced by the country.

The UN's engagement was not only a response to the immediate crises but also a recognition of the interconnection of regional conflicts and their potential to escalate into broader humanitarian disasters. The historical roots of the conflicts in the DRC, intertwined with regional dynamics and power struggles, underscored the need for a coordinated and sustained international effort to bring stability to the region.

By examining these historical events, this paper seeks to provide a contextual framework for understanding the complexities that the UN confronted in its efforts to foster peace and stability in the Democratic Republic of Congo.

United Nations' Engagement in the DRC

The United Nations' engagement in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) has been a longstanding effort to address and resolve the complex challenges faced by the country. The roots of the UN's involvement in the DRC can

be traced back to the early 1960s when the country gained independence from Belgian colonial rule. The political landscape in the aftermath of independence was tumultuous, marked by internal strife and external interventions, prompting the need for international peacekeeping efforts.

One of the earliest instances of the UN's involvement in the DRC was the deployment of peacekeeping forces during the early post-independence period to maintain order and stability. Over the years, the nature and scope of UN missions in the DRC evolved in response to the changing dynamics of conflicts within the region.

One of the significant missions in the UN's engagement with the DRC is the United Nations Organization Stabilization Mission in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (MONUSCO). MONUSCO, established in 2010, represents one of the largest and most complex peacekeeping operations in the world. The mission's mandate encompasses a wide range of objectives, including the protection of civilians, the stabilization of the security situation, the promotion of human rights, and support for political processes and institutions.

MONUSCO's multifaceted approach includes initiatives aimed at disarmament, demobilization, and the reintegration of armed groups. These efforts are crucial in addressing the persistent issue of armed conflicts and violence in the DRC, as various armed groups have operated in the country, leading to widespread human rights abuses and displacement.

Moreover, the protection of civilians has been a primary focus of UN engagement in the DRC. MONUSCO has been tasked with implementing measures to safeguard civilians from violence, including the prevention of sexual and gender-based violence. The mission works in collaboration with the government of the DRC and other international partners to create an environment conducive to lasting peace and development.

> **Strength**

Deployed number of personnel as of February 2023
(Civilian data as of May 2018)

17,753
Total personnel

- 308**
- 2,970** Civilians
- 169** Experts on Mission
- 1,597** Police
- 330** Staff Officer
- 12,379** Troops

Authorised number personnel

16,316
Total uniformed personnel

- 14,000** Military personnel*
- 660** Military observers
- 591** Police
- 1,050** Personnel of formed police units

Challenges Faced by the UN:

The United Nations' commitment to fostering peace in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) has encountered a multitude of challenges, collectively impeding the effectiveness of its interventions. These challenges are rooted in the

unique and intricate nature of the conflicts within the DRC, encompassing a combination of geographical, military, political, and ethical complexities.

1. *Vast Geographical Scope*: The sheer size and vast geographical expanse of the DRC pose a formidable obstacle to effective peacekeeping efforts. The country's diverse terrain, spanning dense rain forests, expansive savannas, and challenging mountainous regions, complicates logistical operations and the deployment of peacekeeping forces (Hooijmaaijers, 2012). This vastness creates challenges in establishing a comprehensive security presence and responding rapidly to emerging crises in remote areas.

2. *Presence of Multiple Armed Groups*: The DRC has been plagued by the presence of numerous armed groups, each with distinct motives and allegiances, contributing to a fragmented security landscape (Autesserre, 2010). These groups operate in various regions of the country, engaging in activities such as resource exploitation, illicit trade, and human rights abuses. Coordinating efforts to disarm and demobilize these groups becomes a complex task, requiring nuanced strategies to address the root causes of their involvement in the conflicts.

3. *Complex Political Landscape*: The political environment in the DRC is marked by historical power struggles, ethnic tensions, and challenges related to governance and corruption (Reyntjens, 2009). The complex interplay of political factions and competing interests complicates efforts to achieve a sustainable political solution. Establishing inclusive governance structures and promoting political dialogue becomes critical for addressing the underlying causes of the conflicts.

4. *Allegations of Misconduct and Sexual Exploitation*: The credibility of UN missions in the DRC has been significantly impacted by allegations of misconduct and sexual exploitation by peacekeeping forces. Instances of abuse by UN personnel have raised serious ethical concerns, undermining the trust of local populations and tarnishing the reputation of the UN (Kingsley, 2019). Addressing these issues requires a concerted effort to enforce accountability mechanisms, strengthen training programs, and uphold the highest standards of conduct among peacekeeping personnel.

Despite these challenges, it is crucial to acknowledge that the UN's role in the DRC remains pivotal, and ongoing efforts are essential to adapt strategies, enhance coordination, and address the multifaceted obstacles to peace in the region.

Achievements and Impact:

Assessing the achievements and impact of the United Nations' (UN) interventions in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) provides a nuanced understanding of the organization's role in addressing the complex and protracted conflicts within the region. This section explores key areas of impact, including successes in disarmament and demobilization, the protective role of peacekeepers for civilians, and efforts to foster political dialogue.

1. *Disarmament and Demobilization*: One of the notable achievements of the UN in the DRC has been its contribution to disarmament and demobilization initiatives. Through missions such as the United Nations Organization Stabilization Mission in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (MONUSCO), concerted efforts have been made to disarm various armed groups and reintegrate former combatants into civilian life (Hehir, 2010). The success in disarming and demobilizing combatants has had positive implications for reducing the overall levels of violence and instability.

2. *Protection of Civilians*: The UN's peacekeeping missions in the DRC have played a crucial role in protecting civilians from the direct impact of armed conflicts. Peacekeepers have been deployed to areas experiencing violence,

contributing to the creation of safe spaces for vulnerable populations (Gilligan, 2012). This protective role has been vital in preventing atrocities, safeguarding civilians from human rights abuses, and facilitating the delivery of humanitarian aid to those in need.

3. *Fostering Political Dialogue*: Efforts to foster political dialogue represent another dimension of the UN's impact in the DRC. The organization has facilitated initiatives aimed at bringing together various political factions to engage in inclusive and constructive dialogue (Dzinesa, 2011). These dialogues have sought to address underlying political grievances, promote reconciliation, and establish frameworks for sustainable governance. While challenges persist in achieving comprehensive political stability, the UN's role in fostering dialogue remains instrumental.

By undertaking a comprehensive evaluation of these achievements, it becomes evident that the UN has made significant contributions to mitigating the impact of conflicts in the DRC. However, it is essential to acknowledge that challenges persist, and the road to lasting stability remains complex.

Achievements and Impact:

This section critically evaluates the United Nations' (UN) interventions in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), focusing on three key areas: disarmament and demobilization, the protective role of peacekeepers, and efforts to foster political dialogue. A thorough analysis of these aspects aims to offer a comprehensive understanding of the UN's impact on conflict resolution in the region.

1. *Disarmament and Demobilization*: The UN's involvement in disarmament and demobilization initiatives in the DRC has witnessed significant achievements. Through missions such as MONUSCO, the UN has played a pivotal role in collecting and destroying weapons, as well as reintegrating former combatants into civilian life (Högbladh, 2015). These efforts have contributed to reducing the overall levels of violence and instability, allowing for the gradual restoration of security in conflict-affected areas. The success of these initiatives is a testament to the UN's commitment to addressing the root causes of conflict and promoting long-term stability.

2. *Protection of Civilians*: Peacekeepers deployed by the UN have played a crucial role in protecting civilians in the DRC, particularly in conflict zones. The presence of UN forces has deterred attacks on vulnerable populations, facilitated humanitarian aid delivery, and created safe spaces for civilians in the midst of ongoing hostilities (Karim, 2012). The protective role of UN peacekeepers has been instrumental in preventing atrocities, human rights abuses, and displacement, thereby contributing to the overall well-being and safety of the local population.

3. *Fostering Political Dialogue*: Efforts to foster political dialogue by the UN have aimed at addressing the underlying political grievances contributing to the conflicts in the DRC. The organization has facilitated inclusive dialogues among various political factions, seeking to build consensus, promote reconciliation, and establish frameworks for sustainable governance (Autesserre, 2016). While challenges persist in achieving comprehensive political stability, the UN's commitment to fostering dialogue has been essential in laying the groundwork for sustainable peace building.

Positive Outcomes and Persistent Challenges: Despite these achievements, persistent challenges in the DRC continue to pose hurdles to lasting stability. The UN faces ongoing difficulties in navigating the complex political landscape, addressing the root causes of conflict, and ensuring the full implementation of disarmament and demobilization programs. Additionally, allegations of misconduct by peacekeeping forces, as well as instances of sexual exploitation, remain critical challenges that impact the credibility of UN missions (Kingsley, 2019).

In conclusion, the achievements and impact of the UN's interventions in the DRC represent a multifaceted landscape. While positive outcomes in disarmament, protection of civilians, and political dialogue are notable, the complex and dynamic nature of the conflicts underscores the ongoing challenges that demand sustained international commitment and adaptation of strategies.

Lessons Learned and Recommendations:

Drawing upon the experiences gleaned from the United Nations' (UN) engagement in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), this section synthesizes valuable insights and puts forth recommendations aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of future peacekeeping missions. The multifaceted nature of conflicts in the DRC provides a rich context for extracting lessons that can inform more nuanced and adaptive approaches to similar challenges globally.

Lessons Learned:

1. **Holistic Approach to Conflict:** One key lesson is the necessity of adopting a holistic approach to conflict resolution. The DRC experience underscores that addressing political, economic, and social dimensions concurrently is essential for sustainable peace (Autesserre, 2014). The interconnection of these factors requires comprehensive strategies that go beyond military interventions to encompass broader peace building initiatives.
2. **Local Ownership and Inclusivity:** The importance of local ownership and inclusivity in peace processes is evident from the DRC. Inclusive participation of local communities, including women and marginalized groups, is critical for building trust, fostering reconciliation, and ensuring the legitimacy of peace building efforts (United Nations, 2015).
3. **Adaptive Strategies:** The fluid and evolving nature of conflicts in the DRC highlights the need for adaptive strategies. Peacekeeping missions must be flexible and responsive, capable of adjusting to changing dynamics on the ground. This adaptability ensures that interventions remain relevant and effective over time (Hehir, 2013).

Recommendations:

1. **Comprehensive Conflict Analysis:** Future peacekeeping missions should begin with a thorough and context-specific conflict analysis. This involves understanding the root causes, dynamics, and local nuances of the conflict, enabling the formulation of targeted and effective strategies (Bellamy, Williams, & Griffin, 2010).
2. **Capacity Building and Institutional Strengthening:** Investing in capacity building and institutional strengthening is crucial for post-conflict reconstruction. This includes support for governance structures, rule of law institutions, and economic development initiatives, addressing the underlying factors that contribute to instability (Autesserre, 2014).
3. **Gender-Sensitive Approaches:** Integrating gender-sensitive approaches is paramount. Women are often disproportionately affected by conflicts, and their active involvement in peace processes contributes to more comprehensive and lasting solutions (Bastick, Grimm, & Kunz, 2007).
4. **Coordination and Collaboration:** Enhanced coordination and collaboration among UN agencies, international partners, and local stakeholders are essential. A cohesive and cooperative approach ensures that

efforts are streamlined, resources are optimized, and interventions are mutually reinforcing (Boutellis & Williams, 2015).

5. **Community-Centrism Interventions:** Prioritizing community-centrism interventions is critical for building trust and resilience at the grassroots level. Understanding and addressing the needs and concerns of local populations contribute to the success of peace building efforts (Mac Ginty, 2010).

In conclusion, the lessons learned from the UN's engagement in the DRC offer valuable insights for shaping the future of peacekeeping missions. By implementing these recommendations, the international community can better navigate the complexities of conflict, promote sustainable peace, and contribute to the well-being of affected populations.

Conclusion:

In retrospect, the United Nations' pivotal role in conflict resolution and peacekeeping missions in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) stands as a defining chapter in the organization's history. The multifaceted nature of the conflicts within the DRC has not only tested the UN's capabilities but has also underscored the intricate challenges inherent in addressing complex crises in the heart of Africa.

The journey of the UN in the DRC, as explored in this research paper, reflects the organization's commitment to maintaining international peace and security. The historical backdrop, marked by cycles of violence, political instability, and regional complexities, served as a crucible for the evolution of UN interventions. From the aftermath of the Rwandan genocide to the power struggles following Mobutu Sese Seko's regime, the UN has been an active participant in the efforts to bring stability and alleviate the suffering of the Congolese people.

This research paper has delved into various dimensions of the UN's engagement in the DRC, from disarmament and demobilization initiatives to the protective role of peacekeepers and efforts to foster political dialogue. The assessment of achievements and impact, as well as the identification of persistent challenges, contributes to a holistic understanding of the UN's influence on conflict resolution in the region.

Moreover, the lessons learned from the UN's experiences in the DRC and the subsequent recommendations provide a road map for refining and enhancing future peacekeeping missions. The importance of a holistic approach, adaptability, and community-centrism interventions emerged as crucial takeaways. These insights not only inform the ongoing efforts in the DRC but also have broader implications for the UN's peacekeeping endeavors worldwide.

As the UN navigates the complexities of conflict resolution, the experiences gained from the DRC underscore the need for continuous reflection, adaptation, and collaboration. The challenges faced and lessons learned in the DRC contribute to the evolving narrative of UN peacekeeping, guiding future initiatives toward more effective, inclusive, and sustainable approaches.

In essence, this research paper contributes to the collective knowledge base on peacekeeping by shedding light on the intricacies of the UN's engagement in the DRC. As the UN continues its mission to uphold peace and security globally, the experiences gleaned from the DRC serve as a testament to the organization's resilience, adaptability, and ongoing commitment to the pursuit of a more peaceful and stable world.

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References

- Autesserre, S. (2010). *The Trouble with the Congo: Local Violence and the Failure of International Peacebuilding*. Cambridge University Press.
- Gberie, L. (2013). *War and Peace in Sierra Leone: Diamonds, Corruption, and the Lebanese Connection*. Pluto Press.
- Hoop Scheffer, J. G. (2008). Speech by NATO Secretary General Jaap de Hoop Scheffer at the Institute for Higher National Defence Studies. Retrieved from <https://www.nato.int/docu/speech/2008/s080702a.html>
- Prunier, G. (2009). *Africa's World War: Congo, the Rwandan Genocide, and the Making of a Continental Catastrophe*. Oxford University Press.
- Reyntjens, F. (2009). *The Great African War: Congo and Regional Geopolitics, 1996-2006*. Cambridge University Press.
- Tull, D. M. (2006). The ADF rebellion and the making of a war of generations in northeastern Congo. *African Studies Review*, 49(3), 31-49.
- Turner, T. (2007). *The Congo Wars: Conflict, Myth and Reality*. London: Zed Books.
- Prunier, G. (2009). *Africa's World War: Congo, the Rwandan Genocide, and the Making of a Continental Catastrophe*. Oxford University Press.
- Reyntjens, F. (2009). *The Great African War: Congo and Regional Geopolitics, 1996-2006*. Cambridge University Press.
- United Nations Security Council. (2010). Resolution 1925 (2010). Retrieved from [https://undocs.org/S/RES/1925\(2010\)](https://undocs.org/S/RES/1925(2010))
- United Nations Organization Stabilization Mission in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (MONUSCO). (n.d.). About MONUSCO. Retrieved from <https://monusco.unmissions.org/en/about-monusco>
- Autesserre, S. (2010). *The Trouble with the Congo: Local Violence and the Failure of International Peacebuilding*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hooijmaaijers, B. (2012). *Peace Operations Seen from Below: UN Missions and Local People*. Routledge.
- Kingsley, P. (2019). UN says 18 peacekeepers killed in attack in Congo. *The New York Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/12/07/world/africa/congo-united-nations-attack.html>
- Reyntjens, F. (2009). *The Great African War: Congo and Regional Geopolitics, 1996-2006*. Cambridge University Press.
- Dzinesa, G. (2011). The UN peacebuilding mission in the Democratic Republic of Congo. *African Security*, 4(3-4), 125-139.
- Gilligan, M. J. (2012). Peacekeeping and Humanitarian Intervention: An Investigation of the Effects of External Interventions on the Duration of Civil Conflicts. *World Politics*, 64(3), 489-525.
- Hehir, A. (2010). *The Responsibility to Protect: Rhetoric, Reality and the Future of Humanitarian Intervention*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- United Nations. (n.d.). United Nations Organization Stabilization Mission in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (MONUSCO). Retrieved from <https://monusco.unmissions.org/>
- Autesserre, S. (2016). *Peaceland: Conflict Resolution and the Everyday Politics of International Intervention*. Cambridge University Press.
- Högladh, S. (2015). The Impact of United Nations Peacekeeping on Political Violence: Evidence from the 1999 East Timor Intervention. *International Studies Quarterly*, 59(3), 487-499.

- Karim, S. M. R. (2012). Civilian Protection in the United Nations Peacekeeping Operations: An Unfulfilled Promise? *Global Governance: A Review of Multilateralism and International Organizations*, 18(1), 89–108.
- Kingsley, P. (2019). UN says 18 peacekeepers killed in attack in Congo. *The New York Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/12/07/world/africa/congo-united-nations-attack.html>
- Autesserre, S. (2014). *Peaceland: Conflict Resolution and the Everyday Politics of International Intervention*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bastick, M., Grimm, K., & Kunz, R. (2007). *Sexual Violence in Armed Conflict: Global Overview and Implications for the Security Sector*. Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces.
- Bellamy, A. J., Williams, P. D., & Griffin, N. (2010). *Understanding Peacekeeping*. Polity.
- Boutellis, A., & Williams, P. D. (2015). The Roots of Coordination Challenges in UN Peace Operations. *International Peacekeeping*, 22(2), 143–159.
- Hehir, A. (2013). *Security and Development in Global Politics: A Critical Comparison*. Georgetown University Press.
- Mac Ginty, R. (2010). Hybrid Peace: The Interaction Between Top-Down and Bottom-Up Peace. *Security Dialogue*, 41(4), 391–412.
- United Nations. (2015). *The Role of Local Actors in the Resolution of the Conflict in the Democratic Republic of the Congo*. Retrieved from <https://www.un.org/News/dh/latest/drcongo-report-030815.pdf>